

An experiment in the communication of four different behavior requests between bottlenose dolphins

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The purpose of this experiment is to investigate whether and, if so, how dolphins are able to communicate certain types of information through acoustic methods. In this experiment, two dolphins (*Tursiops truncatus*) in acoustic but not visual contact must communicate to accomplish one of four specific behavioral tasks. For successful completion, one dolphin must communicate sufficient information to enable another dolphin to identify and perform the correct behavior.

In past experiments (Bastian, 1967; Zanin, Markov and Sidorova, 1990) most similar to our experiment, dolphins were trained to communicate for one specific task. In contrast, we trained dolphins such that a hand signal for “tell” (i.e. “send”) could be prepended to the hand signal for any behavior known by the two dolphins. A dolphin given such a two-part hand signal (i.e. send, followed by the cue for a specific behavior) was trained that she should submerge and produce acoustic signals allowing the “listening” (i.e. “receiver”) dolphin to perform that specific behavior. Although the dolphins were taught the task behaviors through training, their communication mechanisms were not trained. Because the requested behaviors can be varied, we can investigate task-specific differences in the communication methods of the dolphins.

This experiment was performed with two female dolphins, one being the sender and the other the receiver. After training, formal trials were completed in October 2018 using four simple behaviors known by both dolphins, “Clap”, “Come”, “Sing” and “Splash”. Over the course of 10 sessions, each of the four behaviors was tested 30 times. Preliminary analysis of the results showed an overall success rate (i.e. the receiver dolphin performed the correct behavior) of 76.7%. Videos and hydrophone recordings of the sessions have allowed for investigation of the acoustic methods through which the dolphins communicated the necessary information for the requested task, some of which are novel.

This abstract was submitted for the 2019 World Marine Mammal Conference for a poster presentation. Although it was accepted, we were unable to attend the conference. Therefore, the abstract was not archived. B. Doshner is now affiliated with Sea Life Park, Oahu, Hawaii and W. Phillips is now affiliated with Sea World, Queensland, Australia.